

Interview with Music Composer Yasunori Mitsuda

Andrés Domenech Alcaide

CoolJapan.es

In 2019, the CoolJapan.es team travelled to the province of Málaga to attend the MOSMA event, July edition. This year, the event was graced by the presence and work of the celebrated composer Yasunori Mitsuda, beloved by fans of major RPG video game franchises such as the Xeno series —*Xenogears*, *Xenosaga*, and the *Xenoblade Chronicles* games— and, of course, for his work on iconic Super Nintendo and PlayStation titles like *Chrono Trigger* and *Chrono Cross*.

Yasunori Mitsuda with Isabel Vázquez during the fan meet-and-greet held by the composer at the MOSMA 2019 festival.

Yasunori Mitsuda is a versatile composer, adept both with sound chips and full orchestras, effortlessly switching between different musical languages. He is experienced in a wide variety of genres, from traditional Japanese to European music, including Celtic styles. He has collaborated with other great figures in the industry, such as Nobuo Uematsu and Motoi Sakuraba, and from an early age, he achieved success by associating his music with legendary video games. Although his early passion was not music—he even lost interest in piano lessons,

preferring sports instead, as he explains in the interview—a pivotal moment led him into the music and video game industries, where he has brought so much joy to players worldwide.

Mitsuda began his career in the 1990s and quickly demonstrated his talent to Uematsu and other industry veterans such as Hiroki Kikuta, known for the Mana series. Over the years, his work has been associated with Nintendo, Sony, Squaresoft, Monolith Software, and other major companies. He is recognized as a composer who fully immerses himself in the universe he writes for, learning the story, characters, and themes, always showing great respect for each project and, above all, for the fans of his work. As he humorously remarks in the interview, for him, characters and game worlds are essential; all are important, and he even mentions some of his favourite characters outside the formal interview.

During MOSMA 2019, Mitsuda not only performed a magnificent concert covering his career highlights, receiving awards for his work, but also held a fan meeting broadcast live by the event team. Always smiling and approachable, he enjoyed the event as much as his fans and stayed after his scheduled time to continue signing autographs and talking with enthusiasts.

Interview with Yasunori Mitsuda

Cool Japan: Good morning, Mr. Mitsuda. Could you tell us about your vocation? Did you always want to be a composer?

Yasunori Mitsuda: Not at all! I never thought about working in music. I liked sports a lot and wanted to dedicate myself to them as a child. Athletics and swimming interested me greatly. My passion for music came later, after discovering film soundtracks. I then started studying music and later composing myself.

CJ: Can you tell us about your first professional work? Did you start in video games?

YM: I was at a company doing an internship under Sakuraba [Motoi Sakuraba] working with sound. That's when I started enjoying it. It was a very interesting experience and made me realize my interest in composing music professionally.

CJ: Is science fiction one of your favourite genres, given your work in many sci-fi-related games such as the Xeno and Chrono series?

YM: Works like *2001: A Space Odyssey*, *Star Wars*... I know all of them. I've liked science fiction from the start. When I began working with computers, I listened to soundtracks like *Blade Runner*, which I love. Since the Xeno series incorporated sci-fi elements, I felt very comfortable working on it.

Yasunori Mitsuda, having fun while signing for our team, while telling us that his favourite character from Xenoblade Chronicles 2 is Nia, just like our colleague Andrés.

CJ: Your music for the Xeno series (*Xenogears*, *Xenosaga*, *Xenoblade*, etc.), as well as other beloved titles like *Chrono Trigger* and *Chrono Cross*, is widely cherished. What does it mean to you that these games have gained international fame and recognition? You even have a tribute CD, *Time & Space*.

YM: For me, the recognition my work receives both in Japan and abroad, in places as far away as Europe, is incredible. I am very grateful and hope to participate more internationally in the future.

CJ: Continuing with the Xeno series, you created the music for the early titles and participated less in the first *Xenoblade*, though your work is more noticeable in *Xenoblade 2*, collaborating with other composers. How do you feel working on such projects, where your music must integrate with that of others to create a cohesive whole?

YM: It's a fantastic experience and a big responsibility. Everything was thanks to the game director, Tetsuya Takahashi. Takahashi remembered the music from the first games, *Xenogears* and *Xenosaga*, directed by him as well, and in particular liked the theme I composed for *Xenoblade Chronicles*. He specifically asked me to participate in the second game [*Xenoblade Chronicles 2*].

Yasunori Mitsuda —left—, amused while recalling an anecdote during his interview for CoolJapan.es. In the centre, interpreter Arturo Galo Pérez, and in front of him, our colleague at CoolJapan.es, Andrés Domenech Alcaide —right, back to the viewer—.

CJ: *Xenoblade 2* and its expansion have very large soundtracks —over six CDs. What does this say about the current scale of the video game industry?

YM: [Laughs] I think... it's incredible! Six CDs amount to over seven hours of music, which most people wouldn't normally listen to. So yes, I believe this industry surpasses anime even in terms of scale. Video games today are astonishing to me.

CJ: What aspects are most important to you when composing?

YM: There are many things [thoughtful]... For a video game, for instance, it's very important to understand the relationships between characters. Their thoughts, actions, motivations, character, intentions, whether they are good or evil... I also pay attention to their design and appearance. There are many elements I need to consider to create music appropriate for each project, character, and situation. It's difficult to single out the most important thing... Everything is important to me. I am very invested in each project I work on.

CJ: Could you tell us about your preparation, working environment, and influences? What motivates you most when composing?

YM: Generally... a bit of everything. For example, if I watch a movie I like, it motivates me to work. If someone recommends a good soundtrack, I listen to it, and it motivates me greatly. I also listen to music of many genres, not related to soundtracks, which helps me create as well.

CJ: You are an artist with a very diverse background and have worked for systems where, due to technical reasons, only sound chips could be used. Do you prefer working with an orchestra in mind? What stands out most about both methods?

YM: Actually, I don't favour one type of music over another. When asked to compose, I want to create in a way that suits the video game, movie, or project. Neither method—orchestra or chips and synthesiser—is more difficult than the other. I use all the tools both approaches offer. When asked to do something, I just start working on it without finding it difficult, whether it's with an orchestra or not.

CJ: Once storage and media technology allowed vocal tracks in game soundtracks, songs with vocals have remained constant in your work. What attracts you to these compositions, usually featuring female vocals?

YM: It's complicated [laughs]. When composing, the voice is just another tool for musical language. In games, including voices is a complex issue that goes beyond this. For example, when you read a manga, you imagine a character's voice. If adapted to anime, you hear that character's voice, which may differ from what you imagined. In games with no voiced cutscenes, you imagine voices and personalities. It's hard to say whether including vocals is good or bad—it's a really complex topic.

CJ: Perhaps because fantasy became a very popular genre during the 90s, Celtic rhythms appear prominently in your music. Are you attracted to this style?

YM: I love it. I like it very much. Undoubtedly, both Celtic music and classical European music have influenced me. My music comes out that way thanks to these influences.

CJ: Of all your works, which project are you most proud of or remember fondly? Is composing for video games your preferred medium?

YM: They always ask me that [laughs]! Honestly... all my work is important to me. Every project I've participated in I care about equally. I put my heart into all of them, and I believe the audience and players decide which is best for them.

CJ: Finally, could you tell us about any projects you are currently working on or hope to work on in the future?

YM: For the 20th anniversary of *Chrono Cross*, live concerts are planned throughout Japan. Everything is scheduled. And next year, maybe... though I don't have a confirmed date, I'm working on a big project that will be announced soon. I also have a personal goal to release an album of my music.

Yasunori Mitsuda —right—, alongside a family of fans of his work on Xenoblade, Monado in hand

Acknowledgements

We thank the organisers of MOSMA and the Film Music Festival team for making it possible to bring Yasunori Mitsuda to Spain, and for giving us the opportunity to meet and interview him, for their professionalism, kindness toward our team, and their excellent work; especially Juan Ramón Hernández Almagro, always our closest liaison for the event. Of course, we thank Arturo Galo Pérez for his work as interpreter and his kindness, as well as the staff at Hotel Málaga Palacio.

We thank Antonio Jiménez Fuentes for accompanying our team and assisting with images, and, of course, we give our thanks to Yasunori Mitsuda himself, with whom it has been a pleasure to work, and whom we look forward to seeing again in Europe, sharing his talent with all of us. Everything points to this happening, following the very good news provided to us by the Film Music Festival team and Mitsuda himself the same year this interview took place.

Finally, here is the Flickr album where you can see more images of Yasunori Mitsuda at the event, and by following this link, the greeting Mitsuda recorded for the CoolJapan.es team and readers.

Sources

- **Interview written by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es], David Heredia Pitarch [CoolJapan.es], and Miguel Ángel León Ferrer | **Interview conducted by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es] | **Interview interpreted by:** Arturo Galo Pérez

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- *Originally published on CoolJapan.es on January 10, 2020 —Entrevista al compositor Yasunori Mitsuda—*
- *This version is a faithful translation into English by Andrés Domenech Alcaide*